

Folk Psychology without Metaphysics: an expressivist approach

Abstract: In “The Status of Content”, Boghossian considered and rejected an expressivist approach to folk psychology based on its incompatibility with truth-conditional semantics. Given the recent developments of expressivism in philosophical fields such as meta-ethics or epistemology, it is worth re-evaluating the possibility of an expressivist treatment of mental predicates. The aim of this paper is to argue that some of the most influential arguments in favor of expressivism in meta-ethics or meta-epistemology apply to folk psychological predicates (belief and desire ascriptions). Furthermore, I discuss some problems that *folk psychological expressivism* may encounter and propose strategies available for the expressivist to avoid these problems.

1. Introduction

In his critique of irrealism in folk psychology¹, Boghossian (1990) argues against a non-factualist view of mental predicates that he elaborates upon Ayer’s (1936) moral expressivism. Broadly considered, expressivism is a semantic approach according to

¹ According to Boghossian (1990), irrealist positions include eliminativism, instrumentalism and non-factualism (expressivism) because they share the idea that “no real properties answer to central predicates of the region [of discourse] in question” (p. 157). Arguably, expressivism must be considered neither an irrealist nor a realist position because its characteristic maneuver is precisely to avoid that the question about the ontology of such predicates arises.

which the primary function of a specific area of discourse (moral, epistemic or logical expressions, for instance) is not to describe or denote worldly aspects—i.e., the sentences containing these expressions do not state facts. Instead, the concepts under analysis serve different expressive purposes, for instance, expressing conative attitudes, commitments to goals of inquiry or endorsement of inferential connections (Brandom, 2000; Kappel and Moeller, 2013). Regarding folk psychology, Boghossian embraces *incompatibilism*: the thesis that expressivism is not compatible with the standard semantics for natural language, namely, truth-conditional semantics (Pérez-Carballo, 2014: 119). He motivates incompatibilism by putting forward an argument against the coherence between the motivations behind irrealism and alternatives to truth-conditional semantics, such as performative and deflationary theories of truth.

Over the last decades, sophisticated versions of expressivism have emerged in different areas of philosophy, including meta-ethics (Chrisman, 2008; Gibbard, 2003), philosophy of logic (Brandom, 2000), theory of meaning (Gibbard, 2012) and meta-epistemology (Chrisman, 2007; Field, 2009). Several of these approaches aim to reject incompatibilism. Thus, it makes sense to re-evaluate the plausibility of an expressivist treatment of folk psychological ascriptions. This opens several questions: Do these contemporary versions of expressivism avoid Boghossian's critique? Are there contemporary arguments on the expressivist side applicable to folk psychological vocabulary? Does the expressivist treatment of folk psychology encounter particular difficulties?

This paper aims to argue that the main motivations behind classical and contemporary expressivist proposals in the fields of meta-ethics and meta-epistemology can lead us to an expressivist treatment of folk psychology. Anyone who adopt arguments that

motivates expressivism concerning epistemic and moral discourse should accept that these arguments can apply to mental predicates, and thus, motivate an expressivist treatment of mental ascriptions. My main purpose is not to motivate a particular expressivist theory or semantic treatment of mental ascriptions. Instead, the paper aims to provide general strategies that a family of expressivist positions of mental predicates must exploit in order to use some arguments in metaethics and metaepistemology for its own purpose. In this sense, the objective of inquiry of this paper can be understood as a meta-semantic endeavor suggesting different expressivist alternatives that can be exploited in order to apply the mentioned arguments. In section 2, I discuss the anti-ontological motivations behind expressivism and Boghossian's main argument against it. In section 3 and 4, I argue that some of the contemporary arguments for embracing moral and epistemic expressivism in contemporary debates (the practical nature of the concepts under analysis and the phenomenon of evaluative disagreement) can be applied to the case of folk psychological vocabulary. Finally, in section 5, I present a specific problem that expressivism concerning folk psychology must confront, and advance a possible solution.

2. The Ontological Motivation

Firstly, expressivism is the semantic approach according to which the primary function of declarative sentences containing certain groups of expressions (for instance, moral terms) is not to describe the way the world is. Expressivism in meta-ethics emerged as a semantic solution to the ontological problem of making ethical discourse fit into a naturalistic conception of the world. Put simply, expressivism aimed to account for the autonomy of moral and ethical discourse without assuming the existence of *sui generis* entities.

The ontological problem was manifested in the meta-ethical debate between non-naturalist theories which claim that ethical and moral terms refer to or describe *sui generis* entities, and naturalist theories which state that moral terms are reducible or analyzable in natural terms². Contrary to these approaches, the expressivist strategy undermines the semantic assumption behind their ontological positions, namely, *descriptivism*. Descriptivism is the theory according to which the central function a particular area of discourse is to state facts or describe worldly entities. As Chrisman (2007) puts it, descriptivism is the stance whereby it's assumed that "the characteristic function of all indicative sentences is to describe worldly objects, properties, and relations" (p. 227). Likewise, expressivists argue, the ontological problem arises because the positions reviewed above share the assumption that moral terms and statements denote or describe ethical facts.

Now, the main motivation for an expressivist treatment of folk psychology is the existence of an analogous debate concerning the ontology of mental vocabulary. During

²Other two wide-spread views with descriptivist inclinations are the error-theory and fictionalism. According to the error-theory, moral expressions are descriptive terms whose referents are empty; that is, nothing in the world possesses the property denoted by moral concepts. Thus, our moral beliefs are systematically false or erroneous (Mackie, 1977). According to fictionalism, moral discourse is a useful or convenient fiction. In this view, we use terms as immoral or wrong 'as if' they have a referent, which allows its defenders to avoid substantial ontological commitments (Kalderon, 2005). I discuss the application of these positions to the realm of folk psychology below.

the eighties, Paul and Patricia Churchland offered several arguments in favor of Eliminative Materialism. According to this view, our common-sense understanding of the mind is deeply mistaken (P.M. Churchland, 1981; 1984; P.S. Churchland, 1986). Our folk psychological vocabulary refers to theoretical entities that we postulate to understand each other but were discredited by modern neurosciences and neuropsychology. Neurosciences will never find a matchup between our folk psychological concepts and brain states or processes “because our common-sense psychological framework is a false and radically misleading conception of the causes of human behavior and the nature of cognitive activity” (Churchland, 1984, 43).

Eliminative materialism contrasts with two other views. On the one hand, intentional realism (Fodor, 1975) holds that our folk psychological vocabulary refers to real functional states implemented in the brain. In this view, folk psychological concepts represent more or less accurately the mental states and processes underlying our behavior. On the other hand, one may consider that our common-sense conception of the mind is a useful instrument for prediction and explanation without assuming ontological commitments about the nature of the states our mental concepts refer to. This is the position usually ascribed to Dennett (1987, 1991b). According to Dennett (1987), “[f]olk psychology, then, is idealized in that it produces its predictions and explanations by calculating in a normative system; it predicts what we will believe, desire, and do, by determining what we ought to believe, desire, and do” (p. 52). Rather than theorizing about the internal cause of an agent, folk psychology is a strategy to approach behavior based on a simple idealization, which is neutral about the internal architecture of the agent. Dennett’s position is subject to different interpretations. On the one hand, it can be considered as a sort of fictionalism or ‘as if’ instrumentalism: desire and belief

attributions are useful tools for prediction and explanation, yet regarded *as if* they referred to real entities (McCulloch, 1990). On the other hand, Dennett (1991b) has defended that beliefs and desires refer to ‘real patterns’ analogous to centers of gravity that, even if objective, ‘fall short of perfection’.

Note that eliminativism, realism and Dennett’s view share the descriptivist assumption presented above. Firstly, the only way to make eliminativism intelligible is by considering it an error theory. Mental state predicates can be taken as empty terms only if they aim to describe a particular property or object. Secondly, both interpretations of Dennett’s view suppose that our ascriptions are used to describe entities, either abstract or fictional. Finally, for intentional realism mental states predicates are functional descriptions of brain states or reducible to them. As a result, these ontological approaches share the view that folk psychological ascriptions commit their users to the existence of (real, abstract, fictional or erroneous) worldly counterparts. They share the idea that the primary function of declarative sentences in general, and mental states ascriptions in particular, is to describe or state facts. Thus, it is natural to see why one could attempt to exploit the expressivist maneuver for treating folk psychological ascriptions³. On this view, one may

³ At this point, one may question the utility of favoring an expressivist maneuver based on a debate which has not received much attention since the eighties. However, the recent emergence of the so-called narrative approaches to folk psychology has raised several questions concerning its instrumentalist stance and the ontological burden of ascriptions (Andrews, 2007; Hutto, 2013). Furthermore, although these assumptions are not always made explicit, several of the most well-received views in social cognition usually share realist, and therefore, descriptivist, claims concerning the nature of attributions (see, for instance, Apperly, 2011: 5). Thus, motivating an expressivist maneuver on the basis of its implications for the ontological burden of our ascriptions

resist the eliminativist move without undertaking the ontological commitment of fictionalism or realism because the function of folk psychological vocabulary would not describe psychological entities, rather than, for instance, conveying some sort of evaluation or express an evaluative stance (Blackburn, 1998; Dreier, 2004; Evans and Shah, 2012; Köhler, 2017; Toppinen, 2015; see section 3).

Now, why is Boghossian reluctant to put forward the expressivist strategy? According to him, “there is a perspective within the foundation of semantics—specifically, a conception of truth and of truth conditions—from which any such non-factualist view is bound to appear unintelligible” (p. 161). Boghossian is pointing out to the classical position of Ayer (1936), according to which sentences containing moral concepts lack truth conditions or are not ‘truth-apt’. As Boghossian discusses, expressivism is usually introduced along with ‘deflationist’ or ‘performative’ accounts of truth. Regardless of the independent virtues and flaws of these theories of truth, he argues, the problem lies in the tension between these theories and expressivism. The argument goes as follows: Deflationist accounts of truth impose two conditions for a sentence to be truth-deflationist-conditional: to be meaningful (the sentence must be disciplined by norms of correct utterances) and have a declarative form (correct embedding). Given that the concept of truth is just a semantic ascent indicator, there is nothing else to say about ‘P is true’ that asserting P. The tension consists in that those conditions are jointly sufficient for truth-conditionality. There is nothing else to say about the truth-conditions of a sentence except the fact that it is a significant sentence with the appropriate syntax.

is a useful move; not only for the sake of semantic questions concerning ascriptions, but also for its possible benefits for philosophical and scientific theories of social cognition.

However, expressivism denies that certain assertions—namely, those involving normative concepts—are truth-conditional.

Contrary to Ayer's approach, contemporary versions of expressivism attempt to argue against incompatibilism. A common strategy is to offer a *hybrid analysis* of normative statements (Gibbard, 1990, 2003). Gibbard proposes to consider moral statements as the expression of complex mental states consisting of two components: a factual belief and a pro/con attitude. For instance, the sentence 'torturing animals is wrong' uttered by a speaker S is really expressing the following:

- (1) S believes that torturing is not permitted by the set of norms N
- (2) S accepts N

In Gibbard's view, the content of a factual statement can be characterized in terms of the set of possible worlds in which such statement is true. However, the statements involving evaluative notions, as good or wrong, involve what he calls "hyperplans" or pairs "factual normative worlds", which are maximally consistent plans of action or descriptions of the worlds; they tell you what to do in a given situations under possible circumstance. Thus, such hyperplans or 'factual normative worlds $\langle w, n \rangle$ ' include a set of possible worlds (w) and a system of norms (n), which specify what plan must be rejected or permitted in such set of possible worlds. As such, Gibbard's view is compatible with the idea that moral statements do not (only) state facts and with a standard semantic theory in truth-conditional terms; and thus, it can take advantage of Ayer's move while avoiding Boghossian's argument.

Now, can we make an analogous move for mental discourse? Several authors have claimed that mental state ascriptions are evaluative statements which does not describe or state facts (Blackburn, 1998; Drier, 2004; Evans and Shah, 2012; Köhler, 2017; Toppinen, 2015), for instance, some argue that its meaning is not specified in truth-conditional semantics (Blackburn, 1998; Köhler, 2017). However, to exploit the analogy with moral expressivism and avoid the Boghossian's argument, an expressivist treatment of mental ascriptions must maintain (1) that propositional attitude ascriptions are non-descriptive in the relevant sense (non-descriptivism) and (2) that understanding ascriptions in non-descriptive terms is compatible with a standard truth-conditional semantics (compatibilism).

Non-descriptivism about mental state ascriptions is the thesis according to which when a speaker ascribes a mental state like 'Sara believes that it is freezing outside', what the speaker is doing is significantly different from what she does when using a purely descriptive statement like 'the grass is green'. It deserves to be mentioned that non-descriptivism is not a thesis against the existence of mental states or, even against the thesis that we can aim to describe psychological states in certain contexts. Instead, the claim is that our mental state attributions in everyday interactions do not aim to state psychological facts or involve descriptions in the same way that purely descriptive statements, which locate objects, relations and properties in the worlds, do. On the other hand, *compatibilism* is the thesis that non-descriptivism does not requires abandoning our standard semantic theories in truth-conditional terms. In this sense, although some expressivist views maintain that the meaning of ascriptions must not be specified in truth-conditional terms, the object of inquiry of this paper is the family of expressivist theories that aims to jointly maintain (1) and (2); so, they can exploit the virtue of avoiding the

discussion regarding the ontological commitments of folk psychology and at the same time avoid the risk of embracing an alternative semantic analysis.

A move in that direction may take inspiration from Gibbard's work and exploit a *hybrid analysis* of mental state ascriptions. On this approach, when we ascribe a particular mental state we are expressing a proposition characterized in truth-conditional terms but also, given the relevant conditions, we express a particular evaluative attitude. In such a view, non-descriptivism can be regarded as the positive thesis that sentences involving mental states serve to a non-descriptive purpose, for instance, to evaluate the ascribed attitude in accordance with a norm (see Evans and Shah, 2012: 83; Gibbard, 2012: 75-91). Further, such hybrid analysis could be still compatible with a standard semantic theory in truth conditional terms, as far as, mental state ascriptions convey the expression of a proposition which could be specified in factual terms. To see how, consider Bar-on's (2005; see also Bar-on and Chrisman, 2009; and Bar-on and Ochs, 2018) *hybrid expressivist analysis* of self-attributions.

Bar-on (2005) distinguishes between two types of expressions –a-expressions and s-expressions. On the one hand, a person a-expresses a mental state by intentionally doing something. For instance, giving a hug to someone or saying 'it is great to see you', a person is expressing joy; that is, one express approval or disapproval (I like x). On the other hand, a sentence s-expresses an abstract proposition by being a conventional representation of it. For instance, when I say 'it is raining outside', the sentence is s-expressing the proposition that it is raining at time t outside place p (see Bar-on and Chrisman, 2009: 136-137). According to Bar-on, when someone utters a self-ascription such as 'I believe that it is raining outside', she is both conveying a proposition through the statement that s-expresses such proposition (I believe that it is raining outside) and a-

expressing such state of mind. In the case of self-ascriptions, a-expressing a mental state is different from self-reporting such mental state, since such expressive element contributes to the explanation of the distinctive epistemic security of the self-ascriptions (Bar-on, 2005: 240-284). In other words, such a-expressive element allows the subject to know that he is in a particular mental state without further epistemic inquiry.

Although Bar-on's analysis aims at accounting for the epistemic security of self-ascriptions of mental states, the distinction between s-expressing and a-expressing a mental state can also serve to appreciate the distinctive non-descriptive feature of third personal ascriptions. When I say 'Sara believes that it is freezing outside', I am not, or not only, reporting or describing the mental state of Sara, but also a-expressing my own mental states that reflect a particular stance toward Sara. The idea that ascriptions of mental states involve an evaluative stance is not new. Several philosophers (see Blackburn, 1998: 50; Davidson, 1991: 163; Evans and Shah, 2012: 93; Gibbard, 2012: 75-91; Price, 1987; Ramberg, 2000: 359) have argued that ascribing beliefs and desires requires the ascriber to accept a norm or group or norms from which one evaluates the attitude holder⁴. Following this idea, the hybrid expressivist can claim that when one ascribes a mental state, one is a-expressing the acceptance of the prudential, moral or rational norm from which I evaluate the attitude holder. In this view, non-descriptivism is construed as the positive thesis that our ascriptions of mental states aim to express such evaluative stance, and thus, not reporting or describing the attributee's mental state; even though such a report it is necessary as expressive vehicle to perform the evaluation. As

⁴ There is a whole literature regarding the nature of such (see Chignell, 2018 for a review).

For instance, whether or not such norms are prudential, moral or epistemic.

such, the hybrid analysis does not negate that our ascriptions could have a descriptive element which could be specified in truth-conditional terms or even that the meaning our ascriptions somehow relies on a description or reports of mental states. Instead, it emphasizes the disanalogy between pure descriptive statements and evaluative ones.

A second expressivist strategy may attempt to argue for (1) without providing a particular specification of what we are doing when using a mental state ascription. To see how, consider that part of the rationale behind descriptivism regarding mental state ascriptions often relies on the assumption that mental states are relational states between a subject and a proposition (Fodor, 1978: 501). On this approach, concepts such ‘believes’ in sentences such as ‘Sara believes it is freezing outside’ describe a relation between Sara and what she believes. Thus, the form of such propositional attitude ascriptions is ‘ $R(a,b)$ ’ where R describe a relation between two objects, the subject ‘ a ’ and a proposition ‘ b ’. In this sense, the verb ‘believes’ describe a first-order relation such as, for instance, the relation of ‘being on’ in the sentence ‘the telephone is on the table’ ($R(a,b)$). However, there is a whole tradition of analysis of belief that deny the claim that beliefs are first-order relations (Frapolli and Villanueva, 2012; Hintikka, 1962; Kiteley, 1964; Prior, 1971; Recanati, 2000; Stalnaker, 2014; Urmson, 1952). A way to oppose the idea that the expression “believes” is a first-order predicate is to argue that it is a higher-order concepts. Higher-order concepts are functions from propositions to propositions (Frapolli and Villanueva, 2012). According to this view, ‘believe’ would be one such a concept be used to produce proposition of other propositions. For instance, the concept of ‘believes’ can produce a truth-functional proposition (Sara believes that it is freezing outside) taking another proposition as an argument (it is freezing outside). However, one may still

maintain that such concept does not necessarily describe any particular relation or aspect of the world.

Consider Hintikka's (1962; see also, Frapolli & Villanueva: 2012: 482; Stalnaker, 2014: 35-53) analysis of the notions of belief and knowledge. On this view, doxastic and epistemic attributions express a truth-conditional content—the object of the ascription, what someone knows or believes— and instructions about how such a content must be evaluated. When we say 'S believes that p' the expression 'S believes' modifies the circumstances of evaluation of p, prescribing that the truth-conditions of p must be assessed in accordance with a particular subset of the logical space: those worlds which are compatible with S accepting p. The sentence 'Sara believes it is freezing outside' is true if and only if it is freezing outside is true in the logical space compatible with what Sara accepts. At this point, one should notice that representing the possible worlds where Sara accepts the proposition "it is freezing outside" does not requires representing Sara's mental states⁵. Instead, we can understand such a claim as the set of possible worlds where

⁵ One may object that such minimal expressivism does not lack ontological commitments. For instance, it is still committed to a particular ontological position regarding propositional content. However, the point of contention of expressivism is not that our semantic theories do not carry ontological commitments at all. Instead, expressivism is characterized by the idea that by making an evaluation we are not only expressing a proposition, but also expressing evaluative information. Thus, we are not committed with the specific ontological commitment of the existence of the psychological entity that the ascription seems to describe. Thanks to an anonymous referee for bringing my attention to this.

the proposition is true as being said or accepted by Sara (see Gauker, 2003: 215-233 for a similar claim; see also section 5).

Contrary to hybrid expressivism, this version of expressivism, so-called *minimal expressivism* (Frapolli and Villanueva, 2012), is a thesis at the logical-syntactic level. In this sense, the non-descriptivism is construed as the thesis that the logical function of mental predicates is not analogous to first-order predicates. Instead, they function as second-order predicates that provide indications about how the content of the proposition under their scope must be evaluated. Further, given that higher-order operators take propositions specified in truth-conditional terms and produce other propositions, they are compatible with standard truth conditional semantics. However, unlike descriptivism, specifying such true conditions does not require identifying a relation between a subject and a proposition or other analogous descriptive endeavor regarding the mental states of the recipient of the ascription.

As a result, we can find at least two different expressivist strategies to jointly claim that mental states attributions are not descriptive and that such anti-descriptivism is compatible with standard truth-conditional semantics. As such, the central motivation behind moral expressivism according to which we are not necessarily committed to embrace a particular ontological position regarding moral facts can be construed as motivating an analogous move in the context of folk psychology. If ascribing propositional attitudes to a person is not describing her psychological states, we can remain neutral to the discussion about the ontological status of mental states originated by eliminativism.

3. The Practicality Constraint

The second argument for expressivist positions is the so-called practicality constraint or requirement (Horgan and Timmons, 1992; Smith, 1994; Strandberg, 2012). A widespread assumption in meta-ethics is the idea that moral language is practical in a way that other natural language expressions are not. Moral language has a special connection with action—an action-guiding component⁶. This connection is manifested in the inclination or motivation to act in accordance with the moral expressions one utters. Consider, for instance, how unexpected would be to say ‘torturing animals is wrong’ while gambling in a dogfight. Strandberg (2012) defines this special feature of moral language as follows:

The Practicality of Moral Language: It is generally the case that if a person S employs a sentence to the effect that ∂ ing has a certain moral characteristic, such as “ ∂ ing is wrong,” we presume that S has a certain action-guiding attitude in relation to ∂ ing (Strandberg, 2012: 89)

⁶ The special connection between moral concepts and action has been considered a distinctive feature of moral discourse (see Sayre-McCord, 2014). In fact, many meta-ethicists take this connection as a phenomenon any theory about moral discourse must account for. This is the main reason to favor not only expressivism, but other non-cognitivist views in meta-ethics, such as emotivism (Stevenson, 1937) and prescriptivism (Hare, 1952).

Moral language is practical because it serves to regulate each other's patterns of action by encouraging to act, adjusting our behavior or obligating us to abstain from certain acts⁷ (Strandberg, 2012, 89). Certainly, one may question the existence of this connection, but assessing the arguments in favor and against exceeds the reach of this paper. For the purposes of this paper, it is enough to consider that if moral expressivism can be motivated by this connection, then an expressivist treatment of mental predicates can be motivated by the same reason (see Sayre-McCord, 2014)⁸.

⁷ Several authors (Copp, 2009; Finlay, 2005; Potts, 2005), including Strandberg (2012) himself, have argued that the evaluative component of moral or other evaluative expressions can be captured by linguistic mechanisms such as presuppositions, conversational implicatures, or conventional implicatures. The general problem of such views is that the standard theory of conversational and conventional implicatures and presuppositions often characterize them in propositional terms (Grice, 1969), which is at odd with the basic expressivist intuition. Thus, such approaches must choose between providing a plausible expressivist alternative to the standard view of the linguistic mechanism at stake (e.g. presuppositions, see Cepollaro & Stojanovic, 2016) or abandon the expressivist intuition that evaluative meaning is not propositional (for other problems of such views see Buekens 2011).

⁸ In fact, meta-ethicists take this connection as a phenomenon any theory about moral discourse must account for. This is the main reason to favor not only expressivism, but other non-cognitivist views in meta-ethics, such as emotivism (Stevenson, 1937) and prescriptivism (Hare, 1952).

This practical aspect does not seem to be a peculiarity of moral language. Other evaluative expressions predicates display this special connection with action. Actually, defenders of epistemic expressivism have made a similar point concerning knowledge attribution. On this approach, the concept of knowledge has a special connection with behavior, which is manifested in the fact that those who claim to know something regulate and adjust their behavior accordingly (Kappel and Moeller, 2013: 1530-1531). Likewise, when an ascriber (Sara) attributes someone (John) the merit of knowing P, she automatically generates certain expectations regarding his behavior, but more importantly, she will be motivated to reprimand or asked for responsibilities to John if he deviates from the expected behavior; for instance, if he continues inquiring whether P.

Now, an expressivist approach to folk psychological vocabulary could draw an analogy with moral and epistemic concepts. Propositional attitude ascriptions, the expressivists could argue, do not only has an obvious connection with the action of the attitude holder, but also, like in the case of moral or epistemic concepts, with the person who attributes the mental state. As we mentioned in the previous section, several authors (Blackburn, 1998: 50; Davidson, 1991: 163; Evans and Shah, 2012: 93; Gibbard, 2012: 75-91; Price, 1987; Ramberg, 2000: 359) have argued that mental ascriptions involve taking an evaluative stance toward the person we ascribe the attitude. Arguably, such an evaluative stance can explain the disposition or readiness of the ascriber to act in certain ways, e.g. the disposition to regulate, sanction or ask for reasons to those that violate the expected pattern of action. This disposition is manifested, for instance, when we attend to the reactive responses of folk psychologists to the incoherence between ascriptions and actions. McGeer (2015) presents the phenomenon as follows:

we human beings are deeply invested, both practically and emotionally, in regulating one another's thought and action even outside the moral domain. Consider, for instance, how hot under the collar we can get about people who profess certain beliefs and yet do things that are completely at odds with such beliefs – that is, individuals who we disdain as “hypocrites”, notwithstanding the fact that we often instantiate that property ourselves. (McGeer, 2015, 171).

The reaction to this kind of incoherence reveals, of course, that we expect people who avow particular mental states to act as they ought to, according to the ascription. However, the fact that we are ready to regulate, sanction or ask for reasons to those that violate the expected pattern of action, indicate that ascriptions also manifest the ascriber's evaluative stance toward the attitude holder (Andrews, 2012: 155; Zawidzki, 2013: 222-238).

Such evaluative stance also explains recent empirical finding in social psychology which suggest that people, more often than not, ascribe propositional attitudes with the aim of putting the person in question under a positive light (Malle, et al. 2007). Malle and his colleagues found that, when asking people to provide explanations of particular course of action, people often provide more historical factor explanations or enabling factors explanations when they are not the actors. However, such asymmetry is reversed when they are asked to portray the actor in a positive light. In other words, when the subjects were instructed to make the agent look good, they systematically used more explanations in terms of propositional attitudes. Furthermore, people offer many more reasons in terms of mental states when they face puzzling and unexpected actions (Korman and Malle

2016; see also Uttich and Lombrozo 2010) which seem to be circumstances where the subject might feel forced to portray an actor's behavior as reasonable or intelligible. The presence of such evaluative stance may also why people find it extremely difficult to explain actions they strongly condemn, especially when the explanation proceeds in terms of ascriptions (Andrews, 2012: 155). Thus, it is reasonable to think that people provide explanations via mental ascriptions when they are motivated to put the target's action in a positive light.

In a nutshell, mental state ascriptions involve a normative stance toward the attitude holder, which can explain the findings presented above, e.g. the disposition to regulate, sanction or ask for reasons to those that violate the expected pattern of action. In the expressivist view, such stance might lead to draw the analogy with moral and epistemic concepts. If moral and epistemic concepts, which reveal a motivating connection with action, are good candidates for an expressivist treatment, then mental predicates are also good candidates for the expressivist analysis because they exhibit such motivating or evaluative aspect as well⁹.

⁹ One may object that such type of arguments favors the idea that the relevant concepts are evaluative, but does not necessarily favor an expressivist treatment of them (thanks to a referee for noticing me that). Given that, one could maintain that when we ascribe a propositional attitude to someone, we are appealing to certain norms but this is something the descriptivist is ready to assume. Expressivists could reply that there is a genuine difference between describing that something is X according to a norm N, and negatively or positively evaluating something as X according to N (see section 4). Further, such considerations do not affect the conditional claim of this paper. As far as, the argument

Now, the question turns to be whether or not some version of the contemporary expressivism could account for such motivating component. The hybrid expressivism presented above seems to provide a straightforward characterization of such component. As I characterized it, hybrid expressivism holds that when someone expresses a mental ascription “S believes that P”, she is s-expressing or reporting the belief of S and a-expressing her own mental states of support to a particular norm or set of norms from which he evaluates S. Thus, as far as sentences involving evaluative concepts a-express an evaluative attitude, the hybrid expressivist may appeal to this a-expressed attitude to account for the fact that ascriptions have a special connection with the action of the ascriber. For example, if the evaluative attitude is construed as the supportive attitude to a particular norm of rationality, the norm that “believing that p is correct only if it is true that p, and incorrect if it is untrue that p” (Evans and Shah, 2012: 81)¹⁰; we can explain why the ascriber would manifest dispositions to sanction or ask for reasons when the attitude holder violates such a norm. Thus, the hybrid expressivists could maintain that the special connection between mental states ascriptions and the ascribers’ actions depends on the evaluative attitude a-expressed by the ascription.

of practicality belongs the expressivist repertory, I claim that such argument can be used to motivate an expressivist treatment of mental ascriptions.

¹⁰ One may argue that such norms involves a reference (and thus, a description) of particular psychological states. However, as Zawidzki (2013: 152-163) argue, such norms of rationality do not have implications concerning their internal states; that is, the rational idealization is neutral regarding the agent’s inner architecture (see, Author, for a discussion).

Secondly, one can characterize the practicality constraints in terms of the contribution to the conversation. To see how, consider Stalnaker's view (1998) of linguistic communication in terms of possible worlds. According to this theory, the common ground of a conversation is the information that the participants of the conversation commonly presuppose and that the speech acts they perform are designed to influence (Stalnaker, 1998: 98). Such common ground can be modeled in terms of possible worlds, so for instance, when we a speaker assert 'the grass is green' he is modifying the common ground by eliminating the possible worlds where the grass is not green. In general, assertions contribute to a conversation by ruling out possible worlds. However, we need to consider speech acts whose aim is not to rule out possibilities but *open* possibilities (Stalnaker, 2014: 126-127) or ranking possibilities according to different norms (Maitra, 2012) or preferences (Charlow, 2014). Such different contributions to the conversation are manifested in the use of different speech acts, for instance, imperatives. When one says 'eat your vegetables! One instructs one's audience to give preference to the action of eating vegetables over not doing so (Stanley, 2015: 141). Similarly, the use of certain expressions like modal verbs contributes to the common ground without removing possible worlds. For instance, when I claim 'It might be raining outside', I am claiming that it is raining outside is true in some epistemically possible worlds, this means, that the actual world could be located among such possible worlds, and thus, by uttering this sentence, I open the possibility that it is raining outside (Stalnaker, 2014: 237-148; Yalcin, 2007).

Several authors (Pérez-Carballo and Santorio, 2016; Charlow, 2014, 2015; Stalnaker, 2014; Yalcin, 2018) claims that the contribution to the common ground of some of these expressions must be understood in expressivist terms. According to this type of expressivism, so-called *dynamic expressivism*, the speech acts that the sentences

including such expressions are used to perform contrasts with the descriptive information with which assertions modify the common ground. Such contrast can be characterized in different terms (see Stanley, 2015: 125-177 for a review). For instance, Charlow (2014, 2015; see also Lewis, 1979) understand these two different ways of modifying the common ground in terms of the distinction between *locational* and *action-guiding or orientational information*. While locational information enables agents to self-locate themselves in a space of relevant possibilities (by ruling out possible worlds as candidates for the actual world), orientational information enables an agent to order or rank alternative available futures according to a degree of desirability, options or preference (Charlow, 2014: 4-5). For instance, when a speaker claims ‘torturing animals is wrong’, the speaker is contributing to the conversation by ranking the possible worlds in accordance to a particular moral norm that dictate that the worlds where torturing animals is not the case are closer to the actual world¹¹. Sentences that include such expressions can modify the distribution of the possible worlds, and thus, provide action-guiding information about how the speaker or the audience must be disposed to behave.

Taking this on board, one can exploit the dynamic expressivist framework to account for the connection between ascribers’ actions and expressions containing mental vocabulary. In this view, propositional attitude ascriptions modify the common ground by ordering or ranking a set of possible worlds, and thus, providing action-guiding or orientational information about how the speaker or the audience must behave. When a subject uses the ascriptions S believes P, she is not only selecting possible worlds where P is compatible

¹¹ The reason why, for instance, we can disagree about our modal or moral statements even when we agree about all the relevant facts is precisely because orientational information is not locational information (Stalnaker, 2014: Chapter 7; see also section 4)

with what S accepts or selecting those possible worlds where S accepts P. Furthermore, the subject is contributing to the conversation by ranking these worlds in a scale of preferability depending on (rational, social) norms that he endorses. Doing that, the speaker is manifesting an evaluative attitude toward the attitude holder according to such a norm or group of norms; and thus, he is manifesting a disposition to act accordingly (e.g. sanctioning the attitude holder if he does not behave as expected).

Notice that ranking the worlds where S accepts P according to these norms can have different functions depending on the context. For instance, if someone ask me at what time is Anthony's party and I answer "Andres believes it is at 6 o'clock", my utterance aims at modifying the conversational setting by ordering the worlds where Andres believes that the party starts at 6 as being closer to the actual world in accordance with a norm of credibility. For that reason, as some authors (Hazlett 2010; Simons 2007; Urmson 1952) argue, we often use belief ascriptions as indirect evidence that the proposition is true. In other words, we exercise the authority of the attitude holders to claim that the probability that P is true is high. However, in other situations, one can use the order of possible worlds to express that, although P is false, it is still rational to accept P, so the attitude holder must be positively assessed. For instance, when one uses false beliefs to excuse a mistake 'Mary arrived later because She believed that the meeting started at 2', we excuse Mary's behavior by considering it acceptable given certain norms. In both cases, the speaker is expressing her support to certain standards, and thus, expressing her readiness to act accordingly.

As a result, in the dynamic approach, using propositional attitude ascriptions impact the conversational setting by ordering or ranking possible worlds in a scale of normative

preference. By doing that, the speaker is expressing certain action-guiding information, which is translated into different courses of actions (sanctioning Andres if the party does not start at 6; or asking for reasons to Mary if we discover she had the meeting time written in her agenda). This is manifested in the different degrees of responsibility, merit, demerit or conviction toward the attitude holder. Evaluating others by expressing certain orientational information that distributes certain possible worlds in a scale of normative preference is what explain the motivating connection between ascriptions and the behavior of the ascriber.

In a nutshell, statements involving mental states seem to manifest a peculiar connection with the action of the ascriber. Likewise, to the extent that group of expressivist views in the literature can put forward different strategies to account for such component, they can add to the repertory of arguments motivating an expressivist analysis of mental states attribution, the argument of practicality. As such, if the concepts that manifest a special connection with the action of the speaker are good candidates for an expressivist treatment, then mental predicates are also good candidates for the expressivist analysis.

4. Disagreement and the Open Question

The third argument for expressivism involves the analysis of a specific type of disagreements. Disagreement has been widely discussed in many areas of the philosophy of language, such as meta-epistemology, meta-ethics, and semantics of taste predicates (Chrisman, 2007; Cohnitz and Marques, 2013; Field, 2009; López de Sa, 2015; Ridge, 2013; MacFarlane, 2014). The importance of disagreement for expressivism lies in the fact that the expressions which are suitable for an expressivist analysis seem to generate a type of disagreements (evaluative disagreements) which is not produced when only

descriptive expressions are in play (Chrisman, 2007; Field, 2009; Ridge, 2013). The aim of this section is to argue that we can find instances of this type of disagreements involving propositional attitude ascriptions.

In order to see the move, consider the following examples of disagreement:

[1] Shaq: The earth is flat
Kyrie: The earth is not flat

[2] Chris: Waterboarding is wrong
Hitch: Waterboarding is not wrong

The reason disagreements involving moral expressions are interesting is that, in contrast to disagreement involving descriptive expressions, they fail to be solved by appealing to facts. Notice that the disagreement between Shaq and Kyrie can be solved by clearing up the relevant facts, viz. determining whether the earth is flat. Instead, the disagreement between Chris and Hitch does not necessarily dissolve after determining the relevant facts. We can imagine a situation where Chris and Hitch agree on all factual matters and still disagree about whether waterboarding is wrong.

A way to account for this phenomenon is to consider that the propositions expressed by Chris' and Hitch's utterances are relativized to moral norms. The reason Chris and Hitch seem to disagree despite agreeing on the relevant facts is that the truth of the statements depends on certain moral norms. Thus, once the norms are made explicit the disagreement should disappear:

[2]' Chris: According to the Human Rights Declaration, waterboarding is wrong

Hitch: According to the Eight Amendment, waterboarding is not wrong

Notice that making the normative standards explicit would make Chris and Hitch realize they were talking at cross purposes¹². That is, once the standards are made explicit, the initial appearance of disagreement should dissolve (see Chrisman, 2007: 228-230; MacFarlane, 2014: 8-13).

Now, the point of contention for the expressivist is that our intuitions press into the other direction: we can conceive situations where Chris and Hitch do not necessarily resolve their dispute after making the norms explicit. This is another way of putting the classical Moorean open question argument (Moore, 1903: 7, 13; Gibbard, 2012: 33). Chris and Hitch could always reply to each other: 'Ok, according to the norm N, torturing is (not) wrong; but, Is it really wrong or not?'. The reason why the question is still open despite making the norms explicit, Gibbard (2012; see also Field, 2009) argues, is that genuine moral statements have a non-descriptive component. Their meaning cannot be reduced to the fact that, according to a norm, certain action follows. As a conclusion, expressivists argue, when we say that torturing is wrong we are expressing our disapproval of a practice.

This characteristic type of persistent disagreement is not only generated by moral expressions. As Field (2009) has convincingly argued, the same consideration applies to

¹² The disagreement can turn out to be about what the appropriate use of the concept *wrong* is, that is, a 'forward-looking disagreement' (Stojanovic, 2011).

epistemic attributions. In fact, one may expect to find this type of disagreements in any dispute involving evaluative expressions. Now, the question is whether we can find instances of evaluative disagreements involving folk psychological attributions. [Author et al.] have elaborated upon Field's argument to defend that we can identify evaluative disagreements involving belief attributions. Interestingly, they begin with a case that we can actually find in the literature concerning folk psychology. According to Dennett (1978, 1987), propositional attitude ascriptions cannot be anchored in internal states of a subject because ascriptions are always subject to a certain degree of 'indeterminacy'. The patterns that support propositional attitude ascriptions "fall short from perfection, as they always must, there will be uninterpretable gaps; it is always possible in principle for rival intentional stance interpretations of those patterns to tie for first place, so that no further fact could settle what the intentional system in question really believed" (Dennett 1987: 40). As McCulloch claims, Dennett is "denying that there are deep facts concerning what people really believe or desire" (McCulloch 1990, p. 3).

Dennett (1978) makes his point with an example. He invites to consider the case of Sam, an art critic who has promoted the paintings of his son. There are two possible interpretations of this situation: "a) Sam does not believe the paintings are any good, but out of loyalty and love he does this to help his son, or (b) Sam's love for his son has blinded him to the faults of the paintings, and he actually believes they are good" (Dennett, 1978: 39). Now, suppose for the sake of the argument that there exists a reliable way of determining the cause of someone's actions. Imagine, as Dennett does, that we have the technology to write a specific judgment in Sam's brain. Imagine that we write 'my son's paintings are great' at the moment he is promoting his son's paintings. In fact, we can suppose that this was the occurrent cause of the action (promoting his son) at that

moment. Dennett's point is that, even in this extreme case, there are no deep facts we can appeal to in order to decide whether the ascription of this belief is certainly explanatory of the situation. Someone could examine the past and future circumstances of Sam and suspend the interpretation that Sam believes that his son's paintings are good. The interpreter could examine Sam's past behavior and realize that he systematically avoided assessing his son's paintings using the same aesthetics standards that he used for other artists, or that his subsequent behavior is incoherent with the decision of promoting his son's paintings. These circumstances would provide the interpreter with reasons to change his verdict. At the same time, the other interpreter could insist that the accurate ascription is the one that identifies the real cause of the behavior. However, it is dubious whether we can decide which belief ascription is right by appealing to the mere facts. Both interpreters could agree on all the relevant facts and differ on their ascriptions.

Although Dennett presents the case to favor the idea that propositional attitude ascriptions are not anchored in deep facts, the point of contention for [Author] is that the case is an instance of evaluative or normative disagreement. The two speakers disagree about whether we can attribute (to Sam) the belief that his son's paintings are good. Imagine that through the conversation both speakers make explicit different standards of attribution. For instance, Speaker 1 appeals to a norm of coherence; Sam, she argues, does not usually promote the type of art his son's art paintings represent. Thus, he cannot believe that they are good. On the other hand, Speaker 2 appeals to a norm of credibility. He defends that Sam is a well-renowned critic who would not risk his reputation by promoting bad pieces of art. Even when both speakers agree about the relevant facts and they recognize that different standards determine different attributions, they can disagree because they resist abandoning their supportive attitude toward the norm in question

(coherence/credibility). Thus, like moral expressions, belief attributions have an evaluative component supporting standards of attribution.

At this point, one may object that this kind of disagreement does not necessarily motivate an expressivist reading of the relevant concepts; rather, it shows that the concepts involved are normative, in the sense that the standards of coherence and credibility are shifting the contextual parameters that contribute to determine the interpretation. As such, this argument does not necessarily favor an expressivist analysis, but, for instance, certain type of contextualism (Cohen, 1999; DeRose, 1992). On this approach, this type of disagreements reveals the contextual sensitivity of certain vocabulary modulated for the existence of a norm¹³. However, the point of the expressivist is that, if the different norms embraced by the speakers were the source of disagreement, the disagreement should dissolve when the norms are made explicit. Since the disagreement can persist even then, the contextualist reading seems not to be sufficient to account for it. In other words, even if both speakers make explicit their differences regarding their norms of attribution, the disagreement does not necessarily dissolve. It still makes sense to say: “Taking coherence into account, Sam does not believe that the paintings are good; taking credibility into account, Sam does believe the paintings are good but, does he believe it or not?”. The source of the disagreement is not a worldly aspect we could describe or even a norm; rather, it is the speaker’s stance toward the attitude holder which reflect the support to a particular norm¹⁴.

¹³ Thanks to an anonymous reviewer of this journal for bringing this to my attention.

¹⁴ On the dynamic expressivist framework, such a support is manifested in the way the speaker contributes to the conversation by ranking the possible worlds where Sam accepts P. Notice that depending on which norm the ascriber embraces, the ascription will

Summing up, the type of disagreements presented in this section has two special features. First, both parts agree on the relevant facts concerning the attribution. Second, the disagreements do not necessarily dissolve when the standards are made explicit. Both in meta-ethics and meta-epistemology, expressivism takes these features as marking a special character of evaluative concepts that speaks in favor of an expressivist analysis of the concepts in question. Since some disagreements involving propositional attitude ascriptions have the same features, an expressivist view about folk psychological attributions can be supported.

5. The Circularity Risk and the Oblique Strategy

In previous sections, I have attempted to argue that the most wide-spread reasons motivating moral and epistemic expressivism can serve to argue for an expressivist analysis of folk psychological ascriptions. The central goal was to present several strategies and general features that a family of expressivist theories could exploit in order to join the necessary requirements to motivate an expressivist treatment of folk psychological concepts on the basis of other arguments presented in meta-ethics and meta-epistemology.

However, there is a specific challenge that an expressivist analysis of propositional attitude ascriptions must face: the risk of circularity (Dreier, 2002; Shafer-Landau, 2003; Toppinen, 2015; Zangwill, 2010). Consider, for instance, that most representative

contribute differently to the conversational sets, that is, ranking the worlds where Sam accept P closer or farther of the actual world.

versions of moral and epistemic expressivism take our ascriptions to be expressions of complex mental states (see sections 2):

(Expressivism): Normative sentences express desire-like states or states that are constituted by both desire-like states and descriptive beliefs.

Now, the expressivist analysis of folk psychology is based on considering propositional attitude ascriptions as normative sentences, which implies analyzing them in terms of desire-like states:

(Folk Psychological Expressivism) Belief and desire attributions express desire-like states or states that are constituted by both desire-like states and descriptive beliefs.

This definition seems obviously circular. Expressivism is committed to explaining normative judgments in terms of mental states. However, mental state attributions are normative judgments; thus, as Dreier (2002) puts it, “[Expressivism] could not be an explanation of normative judgment. [...] [I]f the aim is to explain normative judgment in general, then using some normative terms in the explanation of others is merely pushing the problem to one side” (p. 139). This way of understanding expressivism is also problematic for another reason, as Sinclair (2009) notices: “to remain distinctive, expressivists must therefore hold that the target judgments express non-belief-like mental states or ‘attitudes’. Thus, the debate moves from a contrast in pure semantics between describing and expressing to a contrast in semantics-cum-psychology between expressing beliefs and expressing attitudes” (p. 136). The concern is that this strategy commits expressivism to a problematic agenda according to which semantics must be understood in psychological terms (Rosen, 1998: 387; Schroeder, 2008: 95-97); besides, it goes

against the anti-ontological aspirations behind the expressivist analysis of folk psychological vocabulary (section 2).

Which kind of strategy could the expressivist follow to avoid this problem? Firstly, a possible way out could be attempting to defend expressivism from the accusation of circularity by undermining the argument itself (Toppinen, 2015). Secondly, one may propose a variety of expressivism that eludes the circularity, for instance, by dropping the claim that expressivism must be couched in psychological terms (see, for instance, Chrisman, 2008). In order to give flesh to this second option, one may begin by elaborating upon what is called *the core expressivist maneuver* (Carter and Chrisman, 2012) or *the oblique strategy* (Gibbard, 2003). For moral expressivism, this maneuver consists in shifting the question about what is ‘good’ to the question of what we do when we say (ask or judge) that (or whether) something is good (Gibbard, 2003: 6).

In the hybrid versions, the expressivist maneuver is approached by paying attention to the type of mental state we are expressing when using moral terms. However, this approach is not the only one. Instead of asking about the mental states that a descriptive or a normative sentence expresses, one could attempt to account for the practical task or function the concept in question accomplishes. This would amount to providing an alternative account, in non-psychological terms, of the distinction between evaluative and descriptive statements.

The dynamic expressivist approaches presented above accomplish this task in terms of the impact of the statements involving the relevant concepts on the conversation. The key aspect is that when we contribute to a particular conversation by providing an ascription,

we are not, or not only, ruling out possible worlds but ranking possible worlds according to a normative preference. For instance, when one claims ‘Sara thinks the bar is closed’, the speaker is ordering the possible worlds where S accepts P according to a norm or set of norms; for instance, a norm of rational credibility. Such an orientation of the possible worlds indicates to other participants of the conversation that the speaker has an evaluative stance toward Sara, and thus, they must expect from the speaker a disposition to perform some linguistic and non-linguistic actions compatible with his evaluation. In principle, specifying how a mental state ascription modifies the conversational setting only requires appealing to the scoreboard of the participants of the conversation. In other words, we can capture the impact of the evaluative nature of propositional attitude ascriptions in terms of the distribution and modifications of the possible worlds of the common ground.

Now, one may object that the dynamic expressivist analysis is not free of psychological entities. First, ascriptions rank possible worlds according to normative preferences which require specifying psychological states of certain kind. Second, if the impact on the conversation of such statements are translated into different subsequent expectations regarding the speaker’s linguistic and non-linguistic behavior is because the conversational contribution expresses one way or another a psychological state that explain the connection with action. After all, characterizing the evaluative stance of the speaker requires to appeal to her mental states, and thus, it is opened to the same circularity risk than others’ expressivist proposals.

However, the orientational information does not necessarily require the ascriber to be in a particular mental state (Schroeder, 2008: 95-97). When a speaker provides orientational

information that exhibit a particular evaluative or practical stance, she is indicating that we are evaluating the attitude holder in accordance to certain norms. Exhibiting such a stance provides specifications to our audience about how they should expect us to act, for instance, as asking for reasons when the recipient of the attribution does not behave as expected or as regulating our own actions in accordance to the norms. Of course, there are psychological states that underpin this stance, but these states are not the focus of attention of the meaning of ascriptions. As Sinclair (2009) says:

“to express a mental state is to take up a public argumentative position with respect that state: to be prepared to defend that state and to advertise this preparedness [...] On this view, the particular territory defended is determined inferentially, by what counts as evidence in favour of one’s stance and what counts as agreement or disagreement. This account also emphasizes that although the territory defended is a mental state, the state itself is not the focus of attention.” (Sinclair, 2009: 142)

In fact, one may think about situations where the speaker performs an insincere ascription which would equally contribute to the conversation, and thus, would put oneself in the relevant position, without the speaker being in the appropriate psychological state¹⁵. As

¹⁵ Geurts (2017) raised a similar point when defending a commitment-based approach to communication. He says: “Commitments are obligations, and although they may be underwritten by suitable mental states, it is not necessary that they are. Insincere commitments are as binding as sincere ones, and there are unintended commitments, too. If I raise my hand at an auction, I thereby commit myself to be making a bid for whatever is currently under the hammer, even if I have no intention of doing so. True, I can try to

such, the risk of circularity disappears as far as the expressivist could account for the appropriate impact of expressive meaning on what we want communicate while avoiding psychology to permeate semantics.

At first glance, such a line of reasoning may lead us to conclude that the dynamic expressivist approach is in a better position to avoid the circularity risk than the hybrid approaches. After all, the hybrid expressivist characterization of evaluative meaning in terms of complex mental states involving a conative and cognitive states seems to be an open to the sort of psychologism at risk of circularity. This is especially obvious, for instance, in Bar-on's hybrid analysis, where felicitously a-expressing a mental state require the speaker to be in the proper psychological state. However, this strong commitment does not seem to necessarily apply to other types of hybrid approaches. In fact, Gibbard seems to be making a move similar to Sinclair when he says "When I say he "expresses" a belief, I don't mean he has that belief. To express a state of mind, as I use the term, is to purport to have it, whether or not one does" (p. 77). In this quote, Gibbard seems to press on the idea that expressing an evaluative attitude does not requires being in a mental state, rather than entitling others to treat oneself as someone who is committed to particular patterns of actions or speech acts in certain circumstances¹⁶.

get out of my commitment, for example, by arguing that I was only waving away a fly, but that presupposes there is a commitment to be undone" (Geurts, 2017: 9).

¹⁶ Certainly, understanding hybrid expressivism in these terms may call for a more detailed explanation of what exactly means to 'purport' to have a mental state. This endeavor may need an explanation that goes beyond the scope of this paper. For our purpose, it is sufficient for acknowledging the possibility that the hybrid expressivism has

When ascribing a propositional attitude, we are taking a particular stance to the person in question, making this person responsible for what she ought to do given her situation, which is translated into treating such person as having certain, duties and entitlements. In other words, we are evaluating the recipient of our ascription as being a rational agent, and thus, as being subject to regulation and sanctions when behaving unexpectedly.

Wrapping up, an often-voiced concern against expressivist analyses presses on the idea that understanding evaluative concepts in terms of the expression of psychological states may turn the approach circular. In this section, I have presented two available strategies that an expressivist treatment of mental predicates can put forward to avoid such a risk. The first strategy elaborates upon the dynamic expressivist framework to open the possibility of understanding expressive meaning in terms of its contribution to the dynamic of the conversation. The second strategy attempts to discard the widespread hybrid expressivist commitment with psychologism by exploiting the disanalogy between being in a mental state or entitling others to treat oneself as being in one.

6. Conclusion

Despite Boghossian's criticism (1990), contemporary versions of expressivism have enough conceptual tools to make an expressivist treatment of folk psychological vocabulary compatible with standard truth-conditional semantics. Furthermore, the expressivist can capitalize on some of the main arguments favoring moral and epistemic expressivism to motivate such analysis of mental predicates. If one finds the arguments

prima facie a route for providing a non-psychologistic explanation of what is to express a mental state.

favoring epistemic and moral expressivism compelling, by the same token, one may embrace an expressivist treatment of mental predicates. Firstly, applying the expressivist maneuver to mental predicates avoids the classical debate concerning the ontological burden of folk psychology. Secondly, treating folk psychological ascriptions as evaluative sentences explains the especial connection between mental concepts and the actions of the ascriber. Finally, belief and desire ascriptions generate a special type of persistent disagreements parallel to those generated by epistemic and moral concepts. These disagreements reveal the evaluative nature of the concepts that motivates an expressivist treatment. Taking these three reasons together allows us to reconsider the plausibility of an expressivist approach to folk psychology.

The main challenge a folk psychological expressivism must meet is addressing the problem of circularity. Some contemporary expressivist views which are compatible with truth-conditional semantics understand normative sentences in terms of complex mental states containing a conative component. Applied to mental predicates, this movement leads to a circular definition of mental state predicates in terms of mental states. However, I have argued, in the literature we can find some ways of solving the problem. In particular, dynamic expressivism has offered analyses that spell out the difference between a normative and a non-normative statement in terms of their contribution to a conversation, rather than in terms of the mental states they express. Further, I have argued that hybrid expressivism may attempt to avoid the challenge by exploiting the disanalogy between being in a mental state or entitling others to treat oneself as being in one. Of course, an expressivist treatment of mental predicates requires further elaboration and probably some of the strategies presented in this paper could turn to be unsuccessful or even incompatible with each other. However, this paper is just an attempt to present some

requirements and strategies that a particular semantic treatment of mental predicates in expressivist terms may develop.

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